

Standard E.M.F. of the Cell

$$\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y \left| \text{HCl} (m_1) \right| \text{HCl} (m_1) \left| \text{HCl} (m_1) \right| \text{AgCl} \left| \text{Ag} \right.$$

$$\left| \text{PbCl}_2(m_2) \right| \left| \text{PbCl}_2(m_2) \right| \left| \text{PbCl}_2(m_2) \right.$$

and Standard Electrode Potential of the $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ Electrode from 5 to 40°C

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The E° of the cell $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y \left| \text{HCl} (m_1) \right| \text{HCl} (m_1) \left| \text{HCl} (m_1) \right| \text{AgCl} \left| \text{Ag} \right.$ has been determined from 5 to 40° at 5° intervals. The standard electrode potential of $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ electrode has been calculated from the known electrode potential of $\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}, \text{Cl}^-$ electrode.

GARRELS and Gucker Jr.¹ recalculated the E° of the cell $\text{Pb}(\text{two phase amalgam}) \left| \text{PbCl}_2(m) \right| \text{AgCl(s)} - \text{Ag} (C_1)$ by feeding the dissociation constant 0.029 of PbCl^+ at 25° from the e.m.f. data of Carmody² as well as Hannan³ and found it to be 0.3430 volt and 0.3433 volt, respectively. When E° of $\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}, \text{Cl}^-$ is subtracted from E° of the cell, E° of $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ comes out to be -0.1205 volt (from Carmody's e.m.f. data) and -0.1208 volt (from Hannan's e.m.f. data) (Stockholm convention).

From the study of the cell

Bates⁴ determined the value of E° of $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ from 5 to 40° at 5° intervals. The value of E° of $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ at 25 was found to be -0.1229 volt (Stockholm convention). When Bates⁴ recalculated the value of E° of $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ from the e.m.f. data of Carmody² by applying Debye-Huckel extended equation, the value came out to be -0.1211 volt at 25° (Stockholm convention).

The value of E° of $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ obtained by different workers^{1,4} differs from each other by about two milli volt even after applying Debye-Huckel extended equation. It was, therefore, decided to redetermine the E° of $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ from 5 to 40° at 5° intervals.

A cell of the type

was employed to determine the E° of $\text{Pb}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Pb}^{2+}$ electrode taking dissociation constant⁵ of PbCl^+

into account. In such a cell, hydrolysis of lead chloride as well as formation of PbOH^+ and its polymers⁶, if any, would be negligible on account of the presence of hydrogen ion in significant amount.

Experimental

The cell (C_3) required solution of HCl and PbCl_2 . The solutions of HCl and PbCl_2 used in cell (C_3) of this paper are the same as of cell (C_1) of an earlier paper⁵. As a matter of fact the same solutions of HCl and PbCl_2 have been used in cell (C_1) of earlier paper⁵ and cell (C_2) of this paper.

Silver-silver chloride electrode was prepared by thermal electrolytic process as recommended by Harned and Ehlers⁷. Lead amalgam electrodes (11% lead) were prepared by the method of Lamer and Parks⁸. The amalgam was cleaned, dried and transferred to electrode vessel by filtering it at 60° through a washed dried piece of muslin till the platinum wire in the vessel was completely covered with the amalgam. The entire operation was done in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Four electrodes thus prepared, on intercomparison gave a potential difference of less than 0.03 mV.

The electrode vessel and bridges were similar to those used by Prasad and coworkers⁹. The cells were set up in the same way as done by Lal and Prasad¹⁰. Measurements were made with a Tinsley vernier potentiometer. The difference in the e.m.f. of the duplicate experiments was less than 0.10 mV. The recorded e.m.f. values are the mean of the duplicate cells. Experimental and other significant data are given in Table 1.

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TABLE I

Mixture of HCl and PbCl		E in abs. volt	$m_{Pb^{2+}} \times 10^3$	$m_{Cl^-} \times 10^3$	$\mu \times 10^3$
$m_1 \times 10^3$	$m_2 \times 10^3$				
Temperature 5°					
2.261	4.515	0.53069	3.572	10.347	13.918
2.516	5.013	0.52764	3.874	11.403	15.277
3.016	6.020	0.52215	4.548	13.584	18.132
3.520	7.023	0.51771	5.100	15.643	20.749
4.013	8.010	0.51390	5.673	17.696	23.368
4.513	9.013	0.51062	6.219	19.745	25.964
5.008	10.037	0.50760	6.768	21.813	28.581
Temperature 10°					
2.260	4.508	0.53348	3.688	10.456	14.144
2.519	5.017	0.53047	3.985	11.520	15.505
3.020	6.025	0.52478	4.658	13.709	18.361
3.522	7.021	0.52050	5.270	15.813	21.093
4.019	8.025	0.51659	5.834	17.878	23.712
4.519	9.031	0.51339	6.365	19.915	26.280
5.013	10.039	0.51026	6.909	21.961	28.870
Temperature 15°					
2.269	4.526	0.53666	3.457	10.252	13.709
2.521	5.026	0.53353	3.733	11.279	15.012
3.024	6.030	0.52800	4.342	13.298	17.739
3.522	7.043	0.52326	4.888	15.463	20.351
4.024	8.043	0.51940	5.410	17.487	22.896
4.526	9.044	0.51613	5.886	19.416	25.252
5.040	10.053	0.51310	6.334	21.427	27.762
Temperature 20°					
2.269	4.524	0.53885	3.464	10.257	13.721
2.522	5.029	0.53578	3.752	11.303	15.055
3.025	6.031	0.53030	4.336	13.392	17.729
3.529	7.035	0.52570	4.822	15.386	20.208
4.035	8.045	0.52182	5.286	17.366	22.654
4.539	9.050	0.51838	5.658	19.247	24.905
5.042	10.052	0.51522	6.104	21.198	27.301
Temperature 25°					
2.259	4.509	0.54179	3.386	10.154	13.540
2.511	5.012	0.53802	3.756	11.279	15.035
3.014	6.015	0.53235	4.302	13.331	17.633
3.510	7.007	0.52757	4.870	15.387	20.257
4.019	8.022	0.52348	5.179	17.238	22.434
4.519	9.019	0.52006	5.675	19.231	24.888
5.020	10.020	0.51702	6.040	21.080	27.120
Temperature 30°					
2.260	4.510	0.54276	3.649	10.419	14.068
2.520	5.017	0.53939	3.966	11.468	15.399
3.018	6.021	0.53355	4.538	13.577	18.115
3.519	7.021	0.52905	5.018	15.558	20.576
4.023	8.031	0.52485	5.543	17.597	23.140
4.520	9.025	0.52137	5.868	19.413	25.261
5.006	10.029	0.51835	6.257	21.292	27.549
Temperature 35°					
2.522	5.032	0.54217	3.626	11.180	14.806
3.024	6.036	0.53640	4.100	13.160	17.261
3.530	7.044	0.53149	4.622	15.196	19.816
4.038	8.056	0.52754	5.049	17.143	22.191
4.541	9.059	0.52382	5.456	19.056	24.512
5.041	10.056	0.52077	5.825	20.922	26.743
Temperature 40°					
2.526	5.039	0.54390	3.241	10.806	14.047
3.032	6.044	0.53835	3.616	12.692	16.308
3.538	7.053	0.53332	4.049	14.640	18.689
4.044	8.055	0.52903	4.499	16.599	21.096
4.552	9.066	0.52540	4.891	18.509	23.400
5.059	10.075	0.52229	5.137	20.271	25.408

Fig. 1. Equation $E + \frac{2.30259 RT}{2F} \left(\log m_{Pb} \cdot m^2 \cdot cl - \frac{3A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} \right) = E^\circ - \frac{2.30259 RT}{2F} \beta \mu$
L. H. S. E. Plotted against μ .

TABLE 2

	Temp. °C							
	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
-E°	0.1117	0.1142	0.1163	0.1184	0.1211	0.1234	0.1241	0.1236
β	0.050	0.044	0.079	0.105	0.153	0.151	0.129	0.120

Discussion

Leaving out the charges on the ions, the e.m.f. of the cells of the type

is given by

$$E = E^\circ - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln m_{Pb} \cdot m_{Cl}^2 \cdot \gamma_{Pb} \cdot \gamma_{Cl}^2 \quad (1)$$

where $E^\circ = E^\circ_{Ag/AgCl, Cl^-} - E^\circ_{Pb_x Hg_y / Pb^{2+}}$ (Stockholm convention).

Applying $-\ln \gamma_i = \frac{AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - B_i \mu$ in equation (1) and

on rearranging, we get

$$E + \frac{2.30259RT}{2F} \log m_{Pb} \cdot m_{Cl}^2 - \frac{2.30259RT}{F} \cdot \frac{3A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = E^\circ - \frac{2.30259RT}{2F} \beta \mu \quad (2)$$

The value of A on molality scale is taken the same as in the earlier paper⁵.

Since the molalities of lead chloride and hydrochloric acid in cell (C₂) of this paper are kept the same as in cell (C₁) of the earlier paper⁵, the actual molalities of Pb²⁺ and Cl⁻ determined from cell (C₁) of earlier paper⁵ have been used in cell (C₂) of this paper. The values of m_{Pb}, m_{Cl} and μ of cell (C₂) of this paper will be the same as in cell (C₁) of the earlier paper⁵. The plot of equation (2) against μ gave a straight line. The intercept at μ=0 gave the value of E° of the cell and β was obtained from the slope of the line. The plot corresponding to equation (2) at 25° is shown in

Fig. 1. Similar plots are obtained at other temperatures also.

The standard electrode potential of silver-silver chloride is known from the work of Harned and Ehlers¹¹; hence E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ is determined. The values of E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ and β as obtained at different temperatures are given in Table 2.

The value of E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ found by the author is in close agreement with the E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ calculated by Garrels and Gucker¹ and Bates⁴ from Carmody's data², but differs considerably with the E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ determined by Bates⁴. So E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ was also determined at 15 and 25° with the help of cell (C₄).

In cell (C₄) of this paper the same solution of HBr and PbBr₂ were used as in cell (C₁) of an earlier paper¹². Hence, actual molalities of m_{Pb} and m_{Br} determined by cell (C₁) of previous paper¹² have been used in cell (C₄) of this paper.

The value of E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ obtained with the use of PbBr₂ and HBr was in close agreement with the values of E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ obtained with the use of PbCl₂ and HCl.

The value of E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ calculated by Bates⁴ from the e.m.f. data of Carmody² after applying Debye-Huckel extended equation at 25° is in close agreement with the E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ of the present authors. The value of E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ determined with the use of HCl and PbCl₂ solution and HBr and PbBr₂ solution are in close agreement. The value of E° of Pb_xHg_y/Pb²⁺ determined by the present authors may, therefore, be taken to be more accurate than the Bates⁴ values.

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